

Review Article

Mathematics Laboratory: Practical Solution to Classroom “Mathemagics” in Schools

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Abstract

Mathematics is a language of science, and its understanding is paramount to any nation that desires growth and development in the 21st century that is technologically driven. Practical mathematical approach in the mathematics laboratory is a panacea and cure to the demonstrated mathematics phobia by many students in class. This paper described what mathematics laboratory should look like, the equipment expected in the laboratory, the setting and the maintenance of the instructional resources, and the principles to guide the behaviours of the mathematics laboratory users. The paper also stressed the need for each school to have functional mathematics laboratory in terms of equipment, and of course good mathematics teachers for the students to acquire the mathematical skills facilitated through laboratory experience.

Keywords: Mathematics Laboratory, Mathematics Laboratory Equipment, Mathematics Laboratory Setting, Mathematical Laboratory Skills, Mathematical Laboratory Maintenance.

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Introduction

Mathematics is the study of numbers, set of points and various abstract elements together with relation between them and operation performed on them. Mathematics goes beyond formula. It gives reasonable explanation to what, how and why, so as to invoke logical thinking that enables one understands how formulas are derived as well as their applications. Adenegan (2014) highlighted the importance of mathematics under four broad functions-utilitarian, cultural, social and personal functions.

Utilitarian functions: It is useful in everyday life that is it serves as a functional tool in studying individual's everyday problems; it is useful as a tool to other discipline, that is, it serves as a hand maiden for explanation of quantitative situations in other subjects such as economics, physics, navigation, finance, biology and even the arts. This service of Mathematics is exceedingly important to future scientists, engineers, technologists, technicians and skilled mechanics; it is useful for national income and budgeting and useful for laying foundation for further education. (2) Cultural functions: It is useful for calculation in local languages and useful for naming objects. (3) Social functions: It is useful in voting, games and lotteries, birth and death rates and population census, and (4) Personal functions: It encourages correct or accurate thinking, allows for cooperation with others to achieve common goals, allows for character building (patience, persistent and perseverance) and remarkably, it makes one to be happy.

Different approaches have been employed to the teaching of mathematics from time immemorial, but the use of instructional resources have been identified as the most meaningful way to approach mathematics teaching. This is because instructional resources reduce mathematical abstractions to a minimum reality of concrete evidence for the understanding of the concept by the learners, aside reducing the stress a teacher goes through in teaching the concept. Sunday, Olaoye and Hauwa (2021) attested to the fact that instructional materials, when properly used in the teaching and learning situation, can arouse and sustain interest necessary for co-opting conceptual thinking and making learning more permanent for students. According to Chinyere and Anaduaka (2013), instructional resources for mathematics teaching are those resources (both human and material) used for stimulating and maintaining interest as well as facilitating learning in the mathematics classroom. Instructional resources enhance the teaching-learning process when adequately and appropriately used. Mathematics instructional resources are kept and used in the school mathematics laboratory.

Teachers of mathematics in schools are sometimes burdened or even get frustrated in setting up a mathematics laboratory. These frustrations ranging from identification of needed mathematics laboratory equipment, maintenance mathematics laboratory equipment, and the code of conduct to guide the laboratory users, are sometimes expressed. To this end, this paper focused on mathematics laboratory equipment, their settings, maintenance, and the safety precaution to be taken by users. Specifically, the paper aimed at defining a mathematics laboratory, listing and identifying mathematical equipment that can be put in a mathematics laboratory and enumerating ways of setting mathematics laboratory in the school.

Mathematics Laboratory

Mathematics laboratory is a space or room set aside for mathematical experiments and practical activities. It is an organized setting where children work in an informal manner, move around, discuss, choose their materials and method, and generally make and discover mathematical facts for themselves. Uwaezuoke and Charles-Ogan (2016) defined mathematics laboratory as a place where students can learn and explore mathematical concepts and verify mathematical facts and theorems through a variety of activities using different materials. According to Adenegan (2014), mathematics laboratory is a unique room or place, with relevant and up-to-date equipment known as instructional materials, designated for the teaching and learning of mathematics and other scientific or research work, whereby a trained and professionally qualified person (mathematics teacher) readily interact with learners (students) on specified set of instructions. Mathematics laboratory is a practical oriented classroom or place where materials useful for the effective teaching and learning of mathematics are kept.

Objectives of a Mathematics Laboratory

According to John (2017), the following are some of the numerous objectives of math laboratory, as it is meant:

- i. To inculcate permanent numeracy in the students.
- ii. To make mathematics learning very meaningful to the students.
- iii. To lay sound basis for scientific and reflective thinking among the students.
- iv. To make mathematics learning exciting and enjoyable to the students.
- v. To enable students comprehend and internalize mathematical knowledge.
- vi. To generate interest in mathematics and provide solid foundation or background in mathematics learning.
- vii. To stimulate and encourage creativity among the students.
- viii. To equip the students to live effectively in our modern age of science and technology.
- ix. To bridge the long gap between mathematical abstracts/theory and concrete/practical.
- x. To provide readily accessible rich manipulative materials to emphasize on learning by doing.
- xi. To develop an attitude of enquiry.
- xii. To remove the weakness of present day mathematics education.
- xiii. To generate interest in the subject.
- xiv. To make the students divergent thinkers.
- xv. It provides a means of practicing cognitive and psychomotor skills.

- xvi. It is a means of experimenting and verifying of mathematical theorems, principles, and axioms which are already known by the students.

Skills Acquired in Mathematics Laboratory

Generally, the following skills are expected to be developed in the students in their mathematics laboratory exposure:

1. The ability to plan an experiment and analyze a mathematical problem into its components parts.
2. The ability to carry out an experiment/improvisation or demonstration.
3. The ability to interpret the result of experiment/improvisation and draw a possible conclusion.

In order to achieve the general skills, the following are the specific mathematical skills

inculcated in the students during mathematics laboratory practice:

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| 1. Observation. | 2. Formulating hypothesis. |
| 3. Measuring. | 4. Classification. |
| 5. Making operational definition. | 6. Manipulating instruments. |
| 7. Counting. | 8. Formulating mathematical models. |
| 9. Communicating. | 10. Manipulating variables. |
| 11. Experimenting. | 12. Predicting. |
| 13. Questioning. | 14. Drawing conclusion. |

Mathematics Laboratory Equipment

The following have been identified as necessary kits that should be made ready in a standard mathematics laboratory. They could be bought from mathematical instructional resources manufacturing companies known for accuracy and precision, or be meticulously constructed by the students and teachers within a period of time. These according to Naugra (2021) include:

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| 1. Geometry shapes | 2. Fraction kits |
| 3. Identity kits | 4. Geometry geo board |
| 5. Geometry geo sticks | 6. Geometry manipulative kits |
| 7. Geometry 2-D kits | 8. Geometry 3-D kits |
| 9. Measurement kits | 10. Number and block kits |
| 11. Pattern and block kits | 12. Place value kits |
| 13. Sort kits | 14. Time kits |
| 15. Trigonometry kits | 16. Data and finance kits |
| 17. Cubes kits | 18. Counting kits |
| 19. Board game kits | 20. Laminated board game |

However, for the purpose of improvisation of instructional resources and other activities in mathematics laboratory, the following equipment are required for mathematics laboratory activities. These according to John (2017) include:

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| 1. Weighing balance/scale.
electric). | 2. Drilling machine (manual or
electric). |
| 3. Drill bit (various sizes). | 4. Engraving machine. |
| 5. Pinchers (big and small). | 6. Hammer (different sizes). |
| 7. Scissors (different sizes). | 8. Hand saw (various sizes). |
| 9. Cardboard papers. | 10. Plywood/softwood. |
| 11. Mathematical set. | 12. Scientific calculator. |
| 13. Nails (different sizes). | 14. Binding wire. |
| 15. Glues and gums. | 16. Sealer tape and masking tape. |
| 17. Graph sheets.
colours). | 18. Beads (assorted sizes and
colours). |
| 19. Threads. | 20. Pliers. |
| 21. Screw driver. | 22. Engine oil and red oil. |
| 23. Paint of different colours. | 24. Measuring tape. |
| 25. Washing hand basin. | 26. First aid kit. |
| 27. Wall clock. | 28. Counting objects (like sticks,
bottle covers). |
| 29. Water and soap. | 30. Large meter ruler and protractor. |

Mathematics Laboratory Setting

In setting a befitting mathematics laboratory for schools, the following considerations according to Adenegan (2014) are important for safety of the users and long lasting of the equipment.

1. Classify the necessary materials required in the laboratory by labeling them with name tags.
2. Gather all related equipment or materials on the same side/place. e.g. geometric objects should not be placed where audio-visual materials are positioned.
3. Place the bulletin board close to the entrance door in case of any information display.
4. Arrange the benches and tables to allow for free movement in the laboratory.
5. Hang relevant pictures and charts on picture rails and boards.
6. The starboard or white board must be positioned where every student can readily see it.
7. Shelves can be constructed for keeping and demarcating materials.
8. Electronic materials such as projector, television, computer, etc., should be properly displayed.

9. Electrification of the laboratory should be professionally done to allow for safety use.
10. Display materials on tables in an organized manner.
11. The laboratory should be set in such a way that it must be well ventilated.
12. Handy materials that can be easily destroyed or lost can be kept in a cabinet or separate shelf.
13. Arrange the materials in places (on tables, shelves, board, etc.) in a way that they can be easily accessed when needed and returned appropriately after use.

Maintenance of Mathematical Equipment

Storage facilities of some kind are necessary in the mathematics laboratory. There should be shelves for chemicals and other equipment such as:

1. Cupboard (for safe keeping of equipment).
2. Engine oil (for lubrication of moving parts).
3. Cabinets (for storing scissors, saws, etc.).
4. Red oil (for preservation and use of saws)
5. Paints (for painting different things).
6. Shelves (for displaying finished mathematical products).

Mathematics Laboratory Rules

Rules are necessary to guide the conduct of mathematics laboratory users. The following rules according to John (2017) should be enforced by the mathematics laboratory attendant to guide mathematics laboratory users. These are:

- 1) Do not work in the mathematics laboratory unless you are supervised or permitted.
- 2) Do not remove anything from the mathematics laboratory unless you are permitted to do so by the math teacher, and must be returned immediately after use.
- 3) Report all faults, damages, injuries or accidents to the mathematics teacher.
- 4) Do not run or rush into the mathematics laboratory.
- 5) Follow all directions or instructions the way they are stated.
- 6) Do not carry out any unauthorized experiments or improvisations in the mathematics laboratory.

Therefore, because of occurrence of injuries and fire breakages, the first aid kit and fire extinguishers should be provided. The first aid kit should contain requirements for treatment of commonest injuries like; cuts, burns, bruises, etc. The following are expected to be found in the first aid kit of a mathematics laboratory:

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| 1. | Adhesive plaster. | 2. Scissors. |
| 3. | Bandages of different sizes. | 4. Sterilized cotton wool packs. |
| 5. | Eye-bath. | 6. Safety pins. |
| 7. | Bottle of mild antiseptic. | 8. Antiseptic ointment. |
| 9. | Eye-bathing solution. | |

It is Paramount to invite a medical officer to advise the students on the content of the first aid kit, how to use it properly and when to use it. The mathematics teacher/students should be conscious of how to make the laboratory safe from all sorts of danger which may arise when working in the mathematics laboratory, because both the teacher and students are exposed to danger. Internal and external injuries may occur when inappropriate technique or equipment is used in the laboratory. The safety rules include:

- 1) Students should be allowed into mathematics laboratory only during mathematical practical/improvisation, when the teacher is present any other exception should be permitted by the mathematics teacher.
- 2) No play or joke is allowed in the mathematics laboratory. It is a place for serious minds, so emphasis should be on activity and not play or joke.
- 3) The students must read very carefully each part of the laboratory experiments or improvisation in order to be aware of what they are going to do and type of apparatus or material required in doing it.
- 4) Students are warned against the use of broken or cracked apparatus or material, because it may be damaged or broken when using it during experiment or improvisation.
- 5) The students are required to read the background material on the activity they want to carry out in the laboratory. They should know the purpose of the lab work and experiences they are required to obtain before entering the laboratory.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Mathematics teaching in 21st century is expected to facilitate and achieve all-round learning of mathematical knowledge and skills in learners, but this will not be achieved without exposure of learners to mathematics laboratory experiences. Skills that are acquired by learners through mathematics laboratory exposure cannot be overemphasized, and no learner should be denied such great virtues in this era. Therefore, this paper hereby strongly recommend that every school authority should make provision for a mathematics laboratory with good equipment, and also employ capable mathematics teachers to make the mathematics laboratory functional. Mathematics laboratory equipment should be kept safe and in good condition at all times.

The setting of mathematics laboratory should allow for safety of users and long lasting of the equipment. Adherence to mathematics laboratory rules should be enforced in order to build maintenance culture in the mathematics laboratory users. Time should be created for mathematics teachers and students to have practical mathematics lesson in mathematics laboratory.

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